

A BRIEF STUDY ON ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS CAUSED BY MINE TAILINGS IN THE IRON QUADRANGLE REGION OF BRAZIL

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ABSTRACT

Mine tailings are a persistent environmental concern, incorporating the waste materials left over after the extraction of valuable minerals from ore. This issue is regularly observed in the region of the Iron Quadrangle, located in the state of Minas Gerais, one of the most important mining sites not just in Brazil, but also globally. This study aimed to make a thorough bibliographical analysis encapsulating the environmental pollution that occurs within the QF region, as a result of arsenic mine tailings produced during intensive mineral activities. The analysis shows signs of ongoing disposal of arsenic-rich mining residues into local drainage systems, which over the centuries has caused nearly 400,000 tons of arsenic waste to settle in the water. Four basins in the Iron Quadrangle area showed levels of high concentration of arsenic in its waters, and further analysis of over 500 sample points revealed widespread contamination throughout the region, mainly affecting rural communities. The results showcase the environmental and social outcomes of inadequate arsenic disposal in streams and watersheds, suggesting urgent initiatives to reduce contamination and ensure the safety of local affected populations and ecosystems.

Keywords: Mine tailings; Iron Quadrangle; Pollution; Arsenic.

INTRODUCTION

Extensive mining activities in the Brazilian southwest state of Minas Gerais commenced in the late 17th century, when the first units of gold-bearing alluvium were discovered in Rio das Velhas, whose springs are located near the city of Ouro Preto [1,2]. The most prominent area regarding mineral processes in Minas Gerais is the Iron Quadrangle region (portuguese: Quadrilátero Ferrífero, also known simply by “QF”), located in the southeast portion of the São Francisco Craton, encompassing an area of approximately 7,000 km² [3]. The region is delimited by the cities of Ouro Preto, Mariana, Congonhas, Caeté and Brumadinho, within other 30 municipalities in its domain [4]. The majority of the metropolitan region of Belo Horizonte, which is the capital and largest city of Minas Gerais, is also found in this locale [4]. The Iron Quadrangle is one of the most prominent mining sites not only in Brazil, but worldwide as well, due to its historical and continued impact in the production of precious metals and gemstones.

While mining activity in the region contributes in extensive ways to the economy and development of both Minas Gerais and Brazil [3,5], such extraction processes inevitably generate a series of environmental problems [6]. It is widely known that metals extracted from the ore during mining activities are not prone to chemical and biological degradation, unlike organic chemicals and plastics [7], thus the by-products of mineral extraction and processing are primitively constituted of residual materials, such as minerals, chemicals and process water [8,9]. This by-product is largely known by scholars as “mine tailings”, a pervasive environmental problem in the Iron Quadrangle [10]. In view of these aspects, this study aims to investigate the main outcomes of environmental pollution in the Iron Quadrangle region spawned by mine tailings, in particular the ones consisting of arsenic.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A bibliographic study was implemented in order to analyze the main causes and effects of mine tailing pollution in the Iron Quadrangle region, with an emphasis on by-products with arsenic on its composition. Firstly, the main objective of the research was defined by the authors, outlining the specific goals of the study and the methodologies that would be employed to attain them. The analysis relied on a scientific research of more than 50 relevant articles and studies, encapsulating characteristics of the Iron Quadrangle area, mine tailings and their resulting pollution. To obtain such studies, tools like Google Scholar and Research Gate were used, where for instance, the words and phrases “ores”, “iron quadrangle” “Minas Gerais geology”, “mine tailings”, “mine tailings pollution” and “arsenic mine tailings” were loaded in the search bar. In a lesser scale, information about the geology and economy of the Iron Quadrangle was arranged from websites and documents provided by the Federal Government of Brazil and the Government of Minas Gerais. In this case, Google Search was used to gather these documents. After several studies had been evaluated, an analysis was composed, focusing on the three main topics addressed in this article: the Iron Quadrangle region, mine tailings and their properties, and the ecological damage of arsenic mine tailings in the QF. These analyses were coalesced and discussed between the authors, to ensure a furnished dissection, underscoring the significant findings and suggestions identified in the literature.

THE IRON QUADRANGLE REGION

The Iron Quadrangle region corresponds to one of the richest and most diverse mineral deposits in the world [11,12], with more than one hundred and fifty minerals in its territory [12]. The five most significant mass-produced commodities in the region are iron, gold, aluminum, manganese and beryllium [13]. Mining activities in the state of Minas Gerais began by gold exploitation in the late 17th century [14,15], however at the outset of the 20th century, iron ores were identified in the Iron Quadrangle, which brought new mineralogical perspectives to the area [1]. The state of Minas Gerais is responsible for more than 50% of Brazil's economic revenue in the iron ore sector [16]. Additionally, Minas Gerais holds 42.53% of the total value of mineral production commercialized in Brazil in the year of 2022 [16].

GEOLOGICAL CONTEXT

The Iron Quadrangle is a Pre-Cambrian structure located in the bounding line between the Geotectonic provinces of São Francisco and Mantiqueira, more precisely in the south portion of the São Francisco Craton [17,18]. Local geology is composed of three main groups: granite-gneiss complexes (Belo Horizonte, Caeté, Baçãõ and Bonfim), archean greenstone belts (Rio das Velhas Supergroup) and Paleo and Mesoproterozoic metasedimentary units (Minas Supergroup, Itacolomi Group and Espinhaço Supergroup) [19]. Rio das Velhas Supergroup is composed of rhyolitic lava, basalt, komatiite and sedimentary rocks [20]; and is divided into two main groups: Nova Lima and Maquiné [11,20]. The Nova Lima Group is a succession of different types of rocks, including: metavolcanic material, quartz ankerite schist, graphitic schists and phyllites [20]. Notably, the region is recognized for holding the most important orogenic gold deposits in the entire QF structure [21]. In contrast, the Maquiné Group contains quartzite, conglomerate and lesser phyllite, and traces of gold are rarely found in the local rocks [22].

The Minas Supergroup is a large metasedimentary sequence primarily consisting of clastic and chemical rocks, located in the southeastern part of the São Francisco Craton [23,24], comprising four groups: Caraça, Itabira, Piracicaba, and Sabará [21]. The Itacolomi group is the youngest Precambrian unit of the Iron Quadrangle, having a constricted areal distribution, limited to the southernmost part of the QF, and is essentially composed of meta-sandstones and meta-conglomerates structures [25,26]. The last Paleo-Mesoproterozoic group to be described in this study is the Espinhaço, composed predominantly of layers of quartzite with conglomerates and metamorphic sericite-schist soft rocks [27,28]. The primary material found in the area is diamonds, more accurately in the Diamantina region [29].

MINE TAILINGS IN THE IRON QUADRANGLE

During the manufacturing processes of mining and metallurgical industries, the endmost goal is to obtain materials of great economic value from the ore [30]. However, the number of valuable metals can vary in every mining site, thus the by-products inevitably emerge within the leftover material from extraction operations [30]. Mine tailings can be found in solid, liquid and gaseous forms, containing toxic substances and chemicals on its compositions [8,31]. They currently lack economic value and compile at mine sites [8]. The chemical and physical characteristics of mining tailings depend on several factors, such as: mineralogy, geochemistry, particle size of the removed material and moisture percentage [8]. The main origins of these materials are sedimentary, metamorphic or igneous rocks, soils, and loose sediments from surface mining activities [8]. Mining tailings in the Iron Quadrangle region have similar mineralogical characteristics, with subtle variations in the mineral proportions [6]. The intensification of mining operations in the Iron Quadrangle has led to an accumulation of waste material, stored as dams, which have attracted global attention due to the tragic incidents of Mariana and Brumadinho in recent years [32,33].

ARSENIC CONTAMINATION

Arsenic (As) is a heavy metal found predominantly in copper, lead and gold ores, and its foremost natural source in the Iron Quadrangle region is rocks containing sulfide gold deposits [34,35,36]. It is known that gold mining is hazardous for the environment, and the by-products of such processes can lead to numerous complications [37], including chemical pollution and severe physical changes in aquatic habitats [38]. Human exposure to arsenic usually occurs through the consumption of contaminated water, but inhalation of arsine and the ingestion of dust generated by polluted soils can also lead to serious contamination [39].

It is believed that the incessant mining processes initiated in the Quadrilátero Ferrífero region in the late 17th century, originated at least 390,000 tons of arsenic, which were constantly ejected into local drainage systems [40]. The anthropogenic origin of arsenic can occur in various ways, including mine tailings and environmental heritage, such as contaminated soil and sediments, old tailings discharge and past activity in old mines [35,40]. In the Ribeirão do Carmo basin, located in the Ouro Preto and Mariana municipalities, arsenic contamination from both old and recent mining activities is evident, as the waste material from gold extraction processes was thrown directly into its alluvial system [39,41]. Sediments accumulated in riverbeds near the Mariana region showed atypical concentrations of arsenic, exhibiting mean levels between 350 and 706 mg/kg [39]. Such concentrations are regarded as extremely high, since the WHO (World Health Organization) defines 10 micrograms per liter (10 µg/L) as the permissible maximum in consumable water [39,42]. It was also perceived that the Ribeirão do Carmo basin showed higher arsenic concentrations compared to other basins, such as Gualaxo do Norte, because of the exacerbated mining industry in the region [39].

Additional research examined more than 500 sample points in the Iron Quadrangle region, covering an area of roughly 7,000 km², in which 26% of the sites analyzed exhibited arsenic concentrations above the quantification limit, which was 0.63 mg/kg [43]. Such high levels of contamination were found in both stream waters and their sediments [43]. The study also showed that the three main basins in the region: Rio das Velhas, Rio Doce and Rio Paraopeba, all indicated values greater than 0.0577 mg/kg [43] which is almost 6 times higher than the safe limit for consumption established by the WHO [42]. In rural areas, the main sources of water supply for the local population are shallow wells and springs [44], which are natural points where groundwater emerges, serving as fundamental components within a greater basin system [45]. Considering the toxicity of the three main basins in the QF area, it is evident that a large portion of the rural population will be affected by the arsenic toxicity in the water [46]. It is also important to highlight that 35 sampling sites analyzed in the previous study are located within rural areas, where the population faces socioeconomic and educational issues, which implies that many of them are unaware of the risks of arsenic exposure [43].

CONCLUSIONS

It is widely known that arsenic poses several risks to human and environmental health. From the evidence gathered, it can be seen that arsenic contamination in streams and watersheds of the Quadrilátero Ferrífero is a recurring problem - approximately 390,000 tons of arsenic have been anthropogenically and continuously dispersed into local drainage systems since the beginning of gold mining activities in the area. Regions that are closer to mining industry sites have higher levels of arsenic in their waters. The three main basins in the region - Rio das Velhas, Rio Doce and Rio Paraopeba - all showed mean values greater than 0.0577 mg/kg, exceeding the World Health Organization's safe consumption limit by almost six times. This situation directly affects public health (SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being) and access to clean water (SDG 6: Clean Water and Sanitation). Several strategies can be executed to address the pollution caused by mine tailings in the Quadrilátero Ferrífero. It is possible to recycle mine waste by converting them into fill material, ceramics, tiles and concrete blocks with aeration [47]. This helps to decrease pollution, while promoting a sustainable economy and accelerating innovations within the civil construction industry (SDG 9: Industry, Innovation & Infrastructure; SDG 11: Sustainable Cities & Communities, SDG 12: Sustainable Consumption and Production). It is also apparent the significance of investing in a robust environmental education (SDG 4: Quality Education), in order to ensure that affected communities acquire knowledge about the risks and viable options regarding arsenic pollution. It is a fact that the mining industry in the Iron Quadrangle is extremely important for the economy of Minas Gerais and Brazil. However, this activity also contributes to environmental challenges, such as degradation of local ecosystems and social impacts in the regional community. This highlights the importance of approaching the impacts of mining wastes on communities and ecosystems in the QF domain, while promoting sustainable practices that prioritize both environmental conservation and local prosperity.

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